

the public to identify which facilities have met government guidelines for captive ownership while highlighting businesses that are keeping lemurs illegally. Similar, albeit voluntary programs, have been used in other regions of the world to identify restaurants that pledge not to sell certain types of foods (e.g. www.fish2fork.com).

Future directions

We acknowledge that the data presented in this paper are preliminary and encourage follow-up studies to examine this subject in greater detail. Additional research and transparency is needed to understand the needs of legal captive facilities and their role in conservation in Madagascar. At the moment, legal captive facilities do not often publicly identify themselves as such and there appears to be little funding to support learning exchanges and collaboration among facilities. Collecting data on this topic is difficult; almost no documents on this topic are available to the public from any of the stakeholders (including government agencies and legal captive facilities).

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Scent marking preferences of ring-tailed lemurs (*Lemur catta*) in spiny forest at Berenty Reserve

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Abstract

Ring-tailed lemurs (*Lemur catta*) scent mark plants for territorial defense and intrasexual competition. We hypothesized that choosing an appropriate plant substrate for marking could be a factor in olfactory communication, as some plants may be easier to scent mark and/or investigate for scent signals than others. We addressed two questions in the spiny forest botanical garden at Berenty Reserve: (1) Which plant genera are scent marked? (2) Which plant morphologies are associated with scent marking? Unlike studies in gallery forest, we found marking occurred disproportionately on the genus *Uncarina*, as well as other plant taxa that are known lemur foods. Marked stems were also more likely to have a smaller stem and forked shape, compared to nearest unmarked neighbors. The genus *Euphorbia*, a plant with sap that is a known irritant to humans, was avoided, even though its morphology appeared suitable for marking. *Uncarina* sap has also been noted for its odor and unique chemistry. Our data suggest that ring-tailed lemur scent marking is strongly associated with certain plant substrates over others, including some with unusual chemical properties. Mechanisms underlying how plant choices facilitate scent communication, or interact chemically with lemur marks, represents a promising area of research. Preferences

we describe are also germane to providing captive lemurs with enrichment to promote natural marking behavior.

Introduction

Lemurs possess arguably the most complex scent marking behavior of all primates (Jolly, 1966; Schilling, 1974). Ring-tailed lemurs (*Lemur catta*) use scent in a variety of social contexts, including territorial defense, mate evaluation, and intrasexual competition (Kappeler, 1998; Jolly, 1966; Merti-Millhollen, 1988, 2006). Both sexes do a “handstand” to place genital marks on substrates at lemur nose height, and males arm-mark plants with metacarpal spurs and glandular secretions from the wrist and armpit, leaving both visual and olfactory signs, often on top of genital marks (Millhollen, 1986; Fig. 1). Kappeler (1998) noted that senders of scent signals cannot control who receives them, comparing the situation to a “bulletin board,” where lemurs transmit signals without a particular intended recipient. Individuals may therefore obtain an advantage in “advertising” their scent by choosing particular plant species or substrates that improve a mark’s attractiveness or stability.

Previous studies of substrate preference in ring-tailed lemurs at Berenty Reserve found no preferences for particular plant species, but strong preference for small, vertical stems (Schilling, 1974; Millhollen, 1986). These studies focused on scent marking behavior during the wet season, when lemurs are more arboreal within closed-canopy gallery forest. However, troops at Berenty also shift during the dry season into relatively open “spiny” forest, dominated by plants in the family Didiereaceae, where scent marking has received relatively less attention (Goodman *et al.*, 2006). Our study describes ring-tailed lemurs’ choices for scent marking during the dry season by answering two questions: (1) Which plant genera are scent marked in the spiny forest? (2) Which plant morphologies are associated with scent marking behavior? We predicted that preferences for small, vertical stems in gallery forest (Schilling, 1974; Millhollen, 1986) would also apply in the spiny forest. Furthermore, we explored whether plant selection was associated with terrestrial marking habits, lemur diet, plant chemistry or anti-herbivore defenses.

Methods

Data were collected at Berenty Reserve (24°58’S, 46°16’E) during the dry season, when ring-tailed lemurs give birth. We followed a habituated troop of 15 lemurs (6 adult females, 7 adult males, and 2 subadult males) from 14 Sept - 19 Nov 2010. Troop members spent most of their time in the spiny forest, where they are often terrestrial and scent mark near ground level.

We also surveyed plants for evidence of past arm and genital scent marking (Fig. 1c) within the outdoor “botanical garden.” The botanical garden (~125 x 70 m) comprised about 20% of the troop’s range and was a major zone of conflict with other troops, making it a good site for surveying plants with scent marks and observing scent marking behavior. In the late 1940’s, Berenty’s garden was established by transplanting plants of all ages from nearby spiny forest. Thus, while the plants in our study reflected those present in natural spiny forest, the relative abundance of each plant species likely differed.

Arm-marking by males often exposes a plant’s underlying green wood and causes visible scars on the stem, whereas genital marking by either sex can leave a visible, oily residue (Fig. 1c). We surveyed all plants with stems in the botanical garden (N = 1911) for evidence of arm or genital marking and identified 1534 to genus. We used binomial tests to de-

Fig. 1: (A) Male lemur stands to arm-marking a forked stem by anchoring with one hand and marking with the other. (B) Female lemur places a genital mark by depositing secretion from the vaginal labia and genital glands on a stem. (C) The branch shown here has evidence of both arm and genital marking. The most heavily marked region of the stem appears as a “marked band”.

termine whether lemurs marked plant taxa in proportion to their relative abundance.

We also observed 100 instances of scent marking by lemurs. Fifty-six observations occurred in the spiny botanical garden. The rest occurred in natural spiny forest (N = 31) or in natural gallery forest (N = 13). For these 100 plants, we measured the height of each scent marking event. We also measured the circumference of marked and nearest unmarked neighbors, both at mark-height and at the plant’s base. Finally, we noted whether the stem was forked (i.e. “Y-shaped”) and estimated the angle of the stem relative to the ground on the scent marked side, (0-180° in 22.5° increments).

We used generalized linear models (binomial family; GLM) in R 3.2 to investigate the relative contributions of morphology and plant taxa associated with scent marking. Marked status (Y/N) was the response variable. Predictor variables included: diameter at mark-height, forked shape (Y/N), stem angle, and plant clade (N = 11). We grouped the 30 genera from the 100 observed markings into families to increase degrees of freedom and eliminated families with fewer than five observations.

We also constructed another series of models that specified salient morphological predictors and further reduced plant taxa. As before, we used these predictors: diameter at marked height, forked shape (Y/N), and stem angle at marking. However, we reduced plant taxa by specifying whether the plant was in the genus *Uncarina* (Y/N) or *Euphorbia* (Y/N), as these genera were the most unusually over- or under-marked, respectively, based on binomial tests of relative abundance (Fig. 2). We also specified whether a plant was part of *L. catta*’s diet (Y/N; based on Simmen *et al.*, 2006), and whether it had spiny bark, which we surmised might reduce marking. We compared all models’ fit using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC).

Fig. 2: Pattern of lemur scent marks by plant genus from survey of the botanical garden at Berenty Reserve. White numbers and grey bars represent marked plants per genus. Total plants surveyed per genus are indicated above each white bar. Black lines indicate expected number of marked plants, based on the null hypothesis (7.8% of each genus - see Results). * $P < 0.01$, ** $P < 0.001$, *** $P < 0.0001$

Results

Of the 1534 individual plant specimens identified in our botanical survey, 7.8% ($N = 120$) exhibited visual evidence of arm-marking or genital marking (Fig. 1). The most frequently marked genus, *Uncarina*, made up only 6.0% of the plant population, yet accounted for 65.0% percent of all the marked plants in the survey (binomial test, $P = 2.54 \times 10^{-80}$; Fig. 2). Members of *Albizia*, *Azadirachta*, *Catharanthus*, *Celtis*, *Fernandoa*, and *Moringa* were also marked significantly more often than expected (Fig. 2; $P < 0.001$). Conversely, scent marks on plants from the genera *Alluaudia*, *Commiphora*, and *Euphorbia* were significantly underrepresented (Fig. 2; $P < 0.01$).

During observations of 100 scent marking events (genital marks = 44, wrist marks = 56), lemurs chose 30 different plant genera in 20 families. Marks occurred at an average height of 41.9 ± 21.9 cm from the plant's base (base diameter = 4.5 ± 3.8 cm). Visible evidence of countermarked scars and oily residue spanned an average 13.7 ± 16.8 cm band along the stem (Fig. 1). Marked plant stems had an average diameter of 3.0 ± 3.5 cm where the mark was placed. Sixty-five percent of marked stems were forked, compared to only 28% of nearest unmarked neighbor plants ($\chi^2 = 27.51$, $df = 1$, $P < 0.0001$). Marked plants were also more likely to grow at acute angles relative to the ground (30% of marked plants did so, compared to only 5% of unmarked neighbors; $\chi^2 = 21.65$, $df = 1$, $P < 0.0001$). Of the 100 marked plants, 27 were in the genus *Uncarina*. Morphology may explain the preponderance of markings on *Uncarina*, as stems averaged 2.6 ± 0.9 cm in diameter at mark height (4.8 ± 1.5 cm at the base), grew at an acute angle ($78^\circ \pm 29^\circ$), and were forked 85% of the time.

The best-fit model from our first analyses included these predictors: diameter at mark height, forked stem, and plant family. ANOVA of model terms indicated that plants with small diameters ($Z = -3.492$, $P = 0.0005$) and forked stems ($Z = 2.460$, $P = 0.0139$) were marked significantly more than expected. Euphorbiaceae, the only plant family included in the best-fit model, was marked significantly less than expected ($N = 27$, $Z = -2.763$, $P = 0.0057$). No other clade, including Pedaliaceae (to which *Uncarina* belongs; $N = 29$, $Z = 1.037$, $P = 0.2996$), was associated with scent marking ($7 \leq N \leq 20$; $-1.383 \leq Z \leq 0.665$, $0.1666 \leq P \leq 0.6537$).

The second series of GLMs yielded a best-fit model in which scent marking was associated with relatively small-diameter plants ($Z = -4.060$, $P < 0.0001$), forked stems ($Z = 2.658$, $P = 0.008$) and genera previously identified as part of the le-

mur diet ($Z = -4.060$, $P < 0.0001$). As before, *Euphorbia* was marked less than expected ($N = 27$, $Z = -3.534$, $P = 0.0004$). The genus *Uncarina* also did not contribute significantly to the model after morphological traits (small diameter, forked stem) were included ($N = 29$, $Z = 0.876$, $P = 0.3813$). Presence of spiny bark also did not contribute significantly to the best-fit model ($N = 18$, $Z = 0.141$, $P = 0.8879$).

Discussion

Ring-tailed lemurs preferentially scent marked seven plant genera in the managed spiny forest habitat at Berenty Reserve, with *Uncarina* disproportionately accounting for marked plants (Fig. 2). *Uncarina*'s morphology, including a small diameter and forked stems, were notably associated with scent marking in GLMs. Preference for small stems occurs year-round, whether *L. catta* is terrestrial in spiny forest (this study) or arboreal in gallery forest (Schilling, 1974; Millhollen, 1986). Forked stems may facilitate terrestrial marks, as males regularly anchor themselves by holding one tine of a forked stem and arm-marking with the other (Fig. 1). Lemur scent marking was also associated with food plants, suggestive of plant ownership. Our result differs from scent marking of sifaka (*Propithecus verreauxi*; Lewis, 2006), possibly because of we used a fairly broad definition of lemur foods, based on published dietary observations at Berenty (Simmen *et al.*, 2006). In contrast, Lewis (2006) identified food plants only when they were consumed just before or after sifaka scent marking.

Lemurs avoided marking the plant genera *Alluaudia*, *Commiphora*, and *Capparis* (Fig. 2), all of which have stems with anti-herbivore defenses (spiny bark). Lemurs also avoided the genus *Euphorbia*, even though its morphological traits, such as small stems and smooth bark, would otherwise appear amenable to scent marking. *Euphorbia*, however, produces a thick, cloying sap known to be an irritant to humans (Webster, 1986), and possibly lemurs as well.

Interestingly, the most marked plant genus, *Uncarina*, produces an odorous sap with unique chemical properties (Yamazaki *et al.*, 2007). Plant-related scent has been associated with fur rubbing behavior in spider monkeys (Campbell, 2000), and sap chemistry can synergistically impact persistence of animal scent on plant surfaces (Soini *et al.*, 1994). Future research on *Uncarina*'s chemistry may reveal a role in lemur chemosignaling.

In conclusion, some substrates, or "bulletin boards," may be better than others for sending and/or receiving chemical signals of ring-tailed lemurs (Kappeler, 1998). We revealed

marking preferences associated with both particular taxa and morphological traits of plants during the dry season, when troops inhabit spiny forest. Preferences are germane to providing captive lemurs with enrichment that promotes natural marking behavior. *Uncarina*, for example, the genus most notably marked, is commonly available in nurseries that specialize in succulents (Harvey, 2014). Other plants, including those with relatively small stems and a forked shape may provide lemurs with equally suitable scent-marking opportunities. Chemical analyses of scent marks on stems would further illuminate how plant substrate choices, and possibly synergistic chemical interactions with plant sap or surfaces, may influence olfactory communication in ring-tailed lemurs.

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Effets de la luminosité et de l'éclairage solaire sur les activités diurnes d'*Eulemur fulvus* dans le Parc National d'Ankarafantsika

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Abstract

We conducted a behavioral study of *Eulemur fulvus* in Ampijoroa station, Ankarafantsika National Park (ANP), to investigate the impact of environmental factors on the diurnal activity of this species from May to June 2012. We used instantaneous focal sampling with an interval of two minutes during the day to collect data on social behavior during different phases of moon illumination, and recorded ambient light levels every 10 min. We found that *Eulemur fulvus* is less active during the day of the full moon period, and its daytime activities increase during new moon phases ($\chi^2 = 38.806$; $p = 0.001$; $ddl = 3$). With regard to the effect of light levels on diurnal activities, travelling and other activities showed a negative correlation with higher light (travel: $r = -0.599$; $p = 0.014$; $N = 16$; other: $r = -0.560$; $p = 0.024$; $N = 16$). Resting was positively correlated with increased light levels ($r = 0.058$; $p = 0.020$; $N = 16$), while feeding and social behaviour were not affected by ambient sunlight (feeding: $p = 0.089$; $N = 16$; social behaviour: $and\ p = 0.234$; $N = 16$). Brown lemurs travel more and are more active under light levels lower than 200 lx, and rest more when light levels are higher than 300 lx.

Introduction

Le Parc National d'Ankarafantsika constitue l'un des plus grands blocs de forêt dense sèche semi caducifoliée de la région Ouest de Madagascar. On y trouve plusieurs types de milieux naturels tels que les forêts denses sèches sur sable; les forêts ripicoles; les forêts raphières; les fourrés xérophiles; les savanes herbeuses (Plan d'aménagement et de gestion-PNA, 2010). Il présente également une caractéristique bioclimatique subhumide chaude qui rendent certaines espèces végétales à développer des caractères biologiques d'adaptation au milieu tels que la brillance des feuilles, la réduction de la surface foliaire, la perte de feuilles pendant la période sèche (Plan d'aménagement et de gestion-PNA, 2010).

En termes de diversité faunistique, le Parc abrite huit espèces de lémurien dont *Eulemur fulvus* qui, depuis 2012, est classée par l'U.I.C.N parmi la catégorie des espèces quasi-menacées (Mittermeier et al., 2014). Il a été noté que chez les lémuridés, une non-adhérence à un cycle d'activité strictement diurne ou nocturne est prévalente (Eppley et al., 2015). Apparemment, deux genres de cette famille (*Eulemur* et *Lemur*) sont cathéméraux. Des hypothèses assument que la cathéméralité représente une adaptation chez les primates; mais d'autres proposent qu'il s'agit du résultat de l'évolution des déséquilibres causée par les impacts hu-